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Reintegrating the Metafield of Power: An Analysis of *The Minerva Controversy* forum

The Minerva Controversy forum¹ offers an appreciably unconstrained and broadminded discussion setting allowing at least two fundamental questions to be raised: one deals with the degree of autonomy intellectuals should possess relative to any form of temporal power in order to produce scientific knowledge and not merely rationalized commonplaces; the other addresses the deontological limits that are to bind expertise. The efforts made by Department of Defense (DOD) personnel to attract more scholars within the institutions' ranks cannot, from a historical point of view, be considered as a staggering "initiative". It is more startling, though, to notice that the polemical project was presented only a few years after the *Behavioral Science Consultation Teams* (BSCT) and *Human Terrain Teams* (HTT) scandals. Other matters of astonishment can be mentioned: the relative enthusiasm that Minerva raised in the academic community, the combination of impetuosity and compliance that characterize most pro-Minerva essays and the rather young age of their authors. Times have obviously changed since the Camelot days. One could also notice that many essays ultimately recycle several of Ithiel de Sola Pool's classical arguments in favor of martial expertise² and that if historians seem to have completely disappeared as military experts, political scientists are still extremely popular within the military (they compose about one third of the 2009 DOD/NSF "winners of technical competition"³). And whereas behaviorist economists and evolutionary psychologists are clearly winning the hearts and minds of US Army Research Office decision makers, cultural or social anthropologists apparently have lost, somehow, the will to work for the DOD.

At a time when the National Science Foundation is partly financing research projects that contain in their titles such unrefined notions as "weak states", "security", "terror", "governance", or "weapons of mass destruction"⁴, it appears urgent to reconstruct (and not deconstruct) the social conditions allowing deeper epistemological breaks to be made. Albeit the "pure" autonomy fantasy has here been denounced as illusory by more than one pro-Minerva author, it is not unnecessary to underline that some kind of autonomy vis-a-vis the temporal pole of the metafield of power was necessary to make outbreaks possible from

¹ <https://items.ssrc.org/category/the-minerva-controversy/>

² See Ithiel de Sola Pool, « The Necessity for Social Scientists Doing Research for Governments », *Background*, vol. 10, n° 2, 1966, pp. 111-122.

³ See *The Minerva Initiative* website : <http://minerva.dtic.mil/funded.html>

⁴ *Ibid.*

prenotions such as the natural inferiority of women, working class members or “colored people”.

Since the DOD regularly finances academic research and runs, as [Ian Roxborough](#) recalled, higher education facilities, research centers, periodicals and, consequently, organic intellectuals, this essay intends to contribute to the understanding of Minerva’s socio-historical significance. It is also aimed at defending a certain idea of scientific practice and intellectual activity without reproving expertise or public commitment as such, to argue that judgmental relativism or fatalism are not adequate postures to apprehend past or present US military applications, and to discuss claims we believe to be sometimes shrewd but often frail. It moreover defends the idea that the re-militarisation of human and social sciences is not an irreversible social process and that its determinants partly lie in the state of the academic and the political field, situations that DOD personnel are taking advantage of with the help of actual or virtual Minervists.

Before going any further, it is necessary to clarify what we mean by “Minervist”. We simply call “Minervists” the forum essayists who defend Minerva with most panache (Minervist will also be used as an adjective). They can be distinguished from others participants, such as those who believe that Minerva represents for the greater part an unfortunate proposal. The sometimes devastating critics advanced in these articles are accompanied by corrective suggestions destined to military or political administrators. The members of these two tendencies make up to this date about two thirds of all participants. Others refuse Minerva on principle without proposing reforms while another minority demonstrates a form of detachment. Although this typology can be discussed, we believe that it is complete and precise enough to comparatively consider and exotize a few Minervist allegations.

Concerning Minerva’s origins, Dr. [Thomas G. Mahnken](#), Deputy Assistant Secretary of Defense for Policy Planning, tactfully exposes his point of view: “*The US government has always turned to the nation’s scholars and intellectuals for help in times of national crises or emergency...*”). Perhaps in order to add some weight to the eternity statement’s explanatory force, [Mr. Mahnken](#) adds that Minerva is also the result of a “desire”, one “*coming from a recognition that the government must do a more thorough job of harnessing [sic] new academic disciplines to help in resolving many of the issues we face*”. This type of (soft) power discourse should of course be taken into account; just as more independent ones. For example, [Priya Satia](#) (who is not considered here as a Minervist) argues that the project is an attempt to resurrect a cold war relationship. The historian writes: “*Having punished defiance by withdrawing the funding that once underpinned the social sciences’ prestige, the government is now trying to woo them back from the sidelines*”. This reminds us that the sixties’ and seventies’ opposition to the militarization of human and social sciences successfully did, in fact and to some extent, contain this type of heteronomization. It also reveals the fatalist essence of claims that call upon (cynical) “realism” to justify Minerva’s existence (for example, [Ronald Krebs](#) thinks that it is “*too late*” while [Paul Bracken](#) believes that: “*even if Minerva is killed it will come back in another form*”).

But why is it apparently so easy to “*woo back*” scholars who once were so “*defiant*”? More generally, why do scholars accept to jeopardize their symbolic capital (in the academic field) by doing research for the DOD (by the way, the DOD is not “the government”)? David Matsumoto, who generously offered to help fight terrorism with evolutionary psychology, explains his engagement in the following terms: “*I happen to fall on the side of getting involved in order to make things better somehow. Others happen to fall on the side of not wanting to be a part of it. That's their choice.*”⁵ Beyond contingency and freedom of choice, [Victor Corona](#) assists us in understanding this problem more sociologically by mentioning the “*social mobility*” and “*limited employment prospects*” that “*many Americans*” encounter. Among other factors, hard times thus believably contribute to the decision of engaging oneself with the military. But there must be a more positive force involved. If, as [Catherine Lutz](#) notes, Minerva is, as we also believe, a “*profoundly nationalist project*” (Catherine Lutz is not a Minervist either), it has to be to some degree supported by homologous social dispositions.

At present, it might help to clarify that we do not consider the DOD as an institutional monolith or a self-governed agency. Not only do many conflicting departments and reasonable people compose it, but actions that come out of it are still more or less tributary to decisions taken in the Department of State. As [Victor Corona](#) and [David Nugent](#) noted, the military not only conduct war, they also provide humanitarian aid. That is a perfectly accurate and charitable remark that needed to be made, especially since this aspect tends to be forgotten: the most recent, without being the best example of disinterestedness, is probably “Operation Unified Response” in Haiti. The military institution is indeed multiple, if not diversely ambiguous. Nevertheless, the people commanding it are “unified” by geostrategic purposes. Recalling the benevolent dimension of the armed forces is useful, but all things considered, it will be burdensome to convince skeptics that Minerva is less about installing oil wells than water pumps.

Likewise, our point is not to say that military institutions or scientific-military advisors are *per se* condemnable. Besides, having serious doubts about present US foreign policy does not presuppose a naïve or mawkish anti-militarist stand. Since not many academic controversies regarding the military uses of human and social sciences against the Nazis seem to have taken place in the early forties (compared to the cold war or the “GWOT”), it is not unreasonable to say that the Office of Strategic Services (OSS) erudites’ engagement enjoyed a high legitimacy.

Confronting today’s weak consensus, [Mr. Krebs](#) believes it is perspicacious to write: “*there is more than a little irony in the fact that those who decry government funding for perverting scholarship owe their jobs, at least indirectly, to such funding*”. First of all, Minerva critics do not condemn “government funding” in general, they reprove “military funding” in particular (did [Hugh Gusterson](#), for example, write anywhere that cancer research should only be

⁵ Scott Jaschik, “First ‘Minerva’ Grants Awarded”, *Inside Higher Ed*, 29 dec. 2008. Web. 3 may 2009 <<http://www.insidehighered.com/news/2008/12/29/minerva>>.

financed by pharmaceutical companies?). Secondly, this claim engages a certain conception of loyalty that, fortunately, is not shared by all State paid intellectuals. And if there is any “irony” to be found here, it perhaps lies in the fact that such a comment can be made by free scholar living in an “open society”.

It is true, however, that political scientists enjoying freedom “*have retained their capacity for critical thinking*”, as [Mr. Krebs](#) argues. Some of them even find time for critical acting: the existence of academic journals like *New Political Science* or scholars such as Irene Gendzier demonstrate it. But perhaps there is some kind of misunderstanding concerning the meaning of criticism. In effect, suggesting, as [Mr Krebs](#) did, that Mr. Gates could have done a slightly better job in bringing “*academic expertise to bear*” can, in fact, be considered as showing some daring spirit, just as criticizing the critics or making irreverent recommendations: “*Minerva currently focuses on what former Secretary of Defense Donald Rumsfeld nicely called ‘known unknowns.’ Why not use some money to explore what Rumsfeld termed ‘unknown unknowns’ [sic]?*”

In Minerva’s case, advising the prince is founded on a postulate that [Ian Roxborough](#) reveals, very nicely also: “*It is better to have a smart military than to have a dumb military*” (depending, of course, on which side you stand). This after all not undisputable apothegm implies that military personnel, when lacking human and social scientists advisors, incline toward the “dumb” flank of the hypothetical intelligence spectrum. This is not a totally shared opinion within the military. Understandably: the RAND 1964 *Viet Cong Motivation and Morale* project obviously had limited effects and the *Human Terrain Teams* are now almost completely discredited⁶. It is remarkable, incidentally, that the unfair “dumb military” stereotype has a positive equivalent within the metafield of power: the supposedly “brilliant diplomat” from the rival Department of State. From this angle, the DOD “need” for more scholars possibly assumes more meaning.

In this uneasy situation, how do Minerva advocates render opposition as difficult as possible? One general tactic is to appeal to scholarly values. At least four of them can be isolated: “discovery”, “dialogue”, “moderation” and “complexity”. [Mr. Roxborough](#) invites us, within the framework of a fellowship, to discover DOD indigenous, “*to place academics in military think-tanks and research institutes for one-year stints*”. But what is presented as an advantage is in reality a problem: the “*one-year tour*” is actually sold as a “*refreshing change*” designed to “*then explain things to our colleagues back in academia*”. There is no need to be a military specialist to notice that this proposition looks more like a PSYOP than a fellowship.

“Discovery” is surely exciting but “dialogue” is virtuous and required in the largest amounts possible. The word appears eight times in [Robert Albro](#)’s essay (declinations of “discussion”, only seven). The professor of communication writes that an academy “*determined to maintain purity-at-a-distance is potentially debilitating to public and democratic debate.*” This

⁶ Information concerning HTT’s uselessness and disrepute within the military field is based on a CERI/Watson Institute conference held in Paris in June 2010 : *Counter-insurgency and “Human Terrain” : The Contested Sites of Contemporary Warfare.*

demagogically astute proposition needs to be examined. First of all, let's note that it tacitly acknowledges that military expertise is, in fact, a profane activity. Furthermore, "*Purity-at-a-distance*" is in this juncture synonymous with "*elitism*" and "*very autonomous*". This deduction is very convenient: military experts turn out to be the undreamt-of guardians of equity. Consequently, the scholars defending proper social conditions for scientific production impersonate the clubby anti-democratic fellows. Among other reasons, academics defend their autonomy and, as a result, the independence of science, because they wish to protect people from "*potentially debilitating*" notions and applications such as, say, Theodore Vallance's exquisite cold war "*cultural engineering*"⁷.

The act of communicating often goes along with a desirably moderate attitude that Minerva critics are, according to their opponents, lacking: one should not exaggerate. Here again, things are strangely twisted since the Minerva controversy is mostly about trespassing limits. Should it be reminded that the ones who are answerable for deontological deviations are not Minerva's contestants? Are those transforming science into instruments of symbolic violence or backing, technically and morally, the "incoherent empire" the moderate savants?

Alongside pleading temperance stands another procedure: propounding "complexity". This, once again, is a tricky tactic to outsmart. How could a scholar write that "epiphenomena" or "big structures" such as Minerva or the DOD are not in fact complex? Minerva, as an expression of the actual re-militarisation of human and social sciences, is indeed a complicated process. But simultaneously, any Iraqi teenager could easily understand its essential purpose. What if the most difficult operations were, in the end, to consolidate, trivialize and develop military-academic relationships?

We noticed that the Minerva coalition was partly presented by [Victor Corona](#) as a solution to an absurdly competitive work setting. It is in a way, undeniably, and many scholars confronted with this context have difficult decisions to make (without always, it is true, rationalizing them as virtuous acts or thinking in terms of "social mobility"). Nevertheless, what might be accommodating for scientists may not be beneficial to science. One way to avoid this type of negative necessity would be, in the first place, to strive for more independence and better working conditions. We also emphasized that the Minerva project not only allows DOD staff to partly make the scientific ruling by distributing favors and exploiting disciplinary segmentations, but that it additionally tends to militarize academic language and categories of thought. In the long run, programs of this sort will, perhaps, succeed in reinforcing the mental and social structures favorable to military-academic collaboration and contribute to the re-integration the US metafield of power. But these joint-ventures may also considerably marginalize academics who "go Army", and therefore dissuade scholars from following the hazardous imperial path. Contemporary geostrategic expertise could even encourage graduate students to engage in upright committed scholarship.

⁷ See Ellen Herman, « Project Camelot and the Career of Cold War Psychology », in Simpson Christopher (Ed.), *Universities and Empire, Money and Politics in the Social Sciences During the Cold War*, New York, The New Press, 1998, pp. 97-133.